

D.5.4 – Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology

WP5 – Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

Authors	Dr Rocio Diaz-Chavez, Imperial College Dr Yara Evans, Imperial College
Contributor	Dr Elizabeth Politzer
Delivery date	30/10/2025
Dissemination level	Public

<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>gEneSys</i>
<i>Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Project Full Title</i>	gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe

© Genesys 2023 This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

GeneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326.

Deliverable Information

<i>Deliverable Name</i>	<i>Identification of criteria for the selection of a model pathway</i>
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public (PU)
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe
<i>Grant Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Contractual date of delivery</i>	30 October 2025
<i>Deliverable Leader</i>	Imperial College
<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	Imperial College
<i>Keywords</i>	GI, gender, energy, energy transition, pathways
<i>Abstract</i>	This report documents the co-creation of pathways to support mainstreaming gender into socio-technical systems. The report is based on achievements of deliverables from work within Genesys and model pathways focused on Education and Policy to sustain the Gender Innovation Approach. The pathways were co-created with key stakeholders during a workshop in Brussels in June 2025 using backcasting methodology. Based on a common vision for 2025, the pathways provide key actions and recommendations to be conducted in 2025 and 2035 to achieve the vision.

Document history

<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Authors</i>
30/10/2025	Draft	Rocio Diaz-Chavez; Yara Evans
		Contributor
20/11/2025		Elizabeth Politzer
		Workshop facilitators
17/06/2025		Rocio Diaz-Chavez; Yara Evans, Elizabeth Politzer, Antonio de Nicola and Serena Tagliacozzo
<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Reviewers</i>
21/11/2025	Draft	Yara Evans

Contents

ACRONYMS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
2. OVERVIEW OF THE ROLE OF GENDER IN THE INTERPRETATIONS OF NET ZERO AND JUST TRANSITIONS.....	10
3. BACKCASTING AND SCENARIO APPROACHES FOR ENERGY PATHWAY DEVELOPMENT WITHIN THE GENESYS PROJECT	11
4. METHODOLOGY	14
5. STORYTELLING REPRESENTATIVE COMMENTS	17
6. FRAMING THE VISION AND PATHWAYS.....	18
7. EDUCATION IN 2025: BUILDING AWARENESS AND INCLUSION.....	20
8. POLICY IN 2025: GOVERNANCE FOUNDATIONS AND VISIBILITY	22
9. OVERLAPS, INTERSECTIONS, AND PATHWAY SYNERGIES	24
10. SYNTHESIS: PATHWAYS TOWARDS THE 2050 VISION.....	29
11. SUMMARY OF KEY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR ACTION BETWEEN 2025 AND 2035 30	
12. CONCLUDING REFLECTIONS	31
13. REFERENCES.....	33
ANNEX 1	35

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. METHODOLOGICAL PROCESS	9
FIGURE 2. IMPACT OF BEHAVIOUR CHANGES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION. (SOURCE: (IEA, 2021).	10
FIGURE 3. BACKCASTING FOR THE GENESYS PROJECT PATHWAYS: EDUCATION AND POLICY (ADAPTED FROM LEUNG, 2016).	14
FIGURE 4. VISION, PATHWAYS, ACTIONS AND MECHANISMS IDENTIFIED BY PARTICIPANTS (JUNE 17 TH , 2025).17	
FIGURE 5. ENERGY PATHWAYS FOCUS AND VISION.	19
FIGURE 6. FRAMING OF GENESYS VISION FOR 2050.	20
FIGURE 7. THE GENESYS PROJECT’S ROADMAP FOR GENDERED PATHWAYS IN EDUCATION AND POLICY.....	31

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. EXAMPLES OF ENERGY TRANSITION PATHWAYS.....	10
TABLE 2. PARTICIPANTS OF THE GENESYS WORKSHOP.....	15

ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial intelligence
BFO	Foundational Ontology
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilisation and storage
DER	Decentralization and Distributed Energy Resources
ERA	European Research
Energy-SHIFTS	Energy Social Science and Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting
ESMAP	Energy Sector Management Assistance Programme
ESO	Energy System Ontology
GEA	Global Energy Assessment
GIA	Gendered Innovation Approach
GBEP	Global Bioenergy Partnership
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
JRC	Joint Research Center
LGBTQIA+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer or questioning, intersex, asexual, and more
PV	Photovoltaic
SET-Plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
UN	United Nations
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organization
WRI	World Resources Institute

Executive Summary

This report of the gEneSys project examines how energy pathways influence gender equality, inclusion, and social justice in the energy transition. It explores the integration of sustainability and equity through frameworks such as socio-technical transitions, environmental justice, and intersectionality. Achieving Net Zero requires pathways that ensure equitable access to affordable, sustainable energy for all. Embedding gender responsiveness and social inclusion is essential to align climate action with just transition objectives.

The Brussels Stakeholders Workshop on gender-just energy transitions, organised under the gEneSys project, brought together experts from education, research, and policy to co-create pathways towards the 2050 vision of *a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy*. Using a backcasting approach, participants worked backwards from this vision to identify the actions and enabling conditions needed in 2025 and 2035 to make it achievable.

Two interdependent pathways framed the exercise: education and policy. These were understood as mutually reinforcing systems essential for embedding gender equality into the European energy transition. Education was regarded as the foundation for awareness, capability, and social learning, while policy was seen as the governance mechanism that institutionalises inclusion and accountability.

In education, the 2025 vision prioritised awareness-raising, access, and interdisciplinarity. Participants proposed reforms to integrate gender and sustainability into curricula, expand opportunities for women through upskilling and scholarships, and strengthen connections between technical and social learning. This early stage was conceived as a period of foundation building, where changes in content, representation, and participation would foster long-term transformation.

By 2035, education was envisioned as a driver of institutional and cultural change. Interdisciplinarity, gender-balanced leadership, and data-driven transparency were seen as integral features of higher education. Equality was no longer treated as an add-on but as a defining characteristic of how knowledge is produced and shared. Education was also positioned as a bridge between research and policy, ensuring that gender-informed knowledge contributes directly to decision-making.

In policy, the 2025 actions focused on establishing frameworks and accountability systems. Participants identified the need for gender-disaggregated data, financial mechanisms with clear gender earmarks, and guidelines for companies and policymakers to mainstream equality. Policy was viewed as the instrument through which the principles of fairness and inclusion would become measurable and enforceable.

By 2035, the policy pathway was characterised by integration and consolidation. Equality was envisioned as embedded within governance structures through regulatory commitments, monitoring, and intersectional measures addressing energy poverty. Participatory mechanisms were expected to empower women and youth in shaping energy decisions. Cultural and institutional change complemented these structural reforms, transforming inclusion into an established norm rather than an exceptional aim.

Across both pathways, participants identified five cross-cutting priorities: data, interdisciplinarity, representation, cultural transformation, and economic incentives. Data provides the foundation for evidence-based decisions; interdisciplinarity connects knowledge and governance; representation

Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology

ensures legitimacy and diversity; cultural change sustains progress; and financial tools translate principles into practice.

Together, the education and policy pathways form a coherent sequence. The 2025 stage establishes awareness and structure, the 2035 stage integrates and consolidates, and the 2050 vision realises the normalisation of equality. The workshop's collective outcome presents a model of systemic change in which gender justice is inseparable from sustainability. Equality, in this vision, is not an end-state but the condition that enables the energy transition to be just, inclusive, and enduring.

1. Introduction

The gEneSys project's aims are to advance understanding of gender dimension in energy research, innovation, and socio-economic development to help accelerate the renewable energy transition and create more gender equitable and just sustainable energy solutions (gEneSys, 2024). gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems, each with its own sustainability visions, implementation concerns, power relations, values and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholders, yet linked so that events and changes in individual subsystem may also influence developments in other subsystems. There is a focus on understanding interactions between gender and energy, which cover energy policies, access, and usage and potentially different impacts on men and women due to their different societal roles, responsibilities, and power structures (UNWomen and UNIDO, 2023). One of the activities of the project (WP5) centres on the development of credible energy transition pathways that are equitable and just.

Several theories and frameworks support a social just energy transition by providing insights into the intersection of energy systems, social equity, and sustainability such as socio-technical transitions theory, environmental justice theory or intersectionality theory. Globally the Net Zero has been stated as the goal to achieve to reduce GHG emission. In order to achieve this goal, different mitigation measures are being implemented including energy transition and this energy transition revolves around pathways to achieve it. Addressing social justice within energy pathways involves ensuring equitable access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy resources for all communities, regardless of socioeconomic status, geographic location, or demographic characteristics.

This report presents the results of a backcasting workshop following the methodology of the gEneSys project to create a “model” pathway and co-develop pathways that are necessary to achieve a gendered social equal just transition under an iterative process where the criteria and pathways can feedback (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Methodological process

2. Overview of the Role of Gender in the Interpretations of Net Zero and Just Transitions

Net Zero and Just Transition concepts interact within gender-responsive energy pathways. *Net Zero*, achieving a balance between greenhouse-gas emissions and removals, is a technical and policy goal central to limiting global warming to 1.5 °C (UN, 2024; IEA, 2021). Yet, major global roadmaps (IEA 2021; IRENA 2024; IPCC 2018) remain largely **gender-blind**, emphasising technologies and economic shifts without adequately considering gendered inequalities or social inclusion.

The *gEneSys* project highlights that equitable energy transitions require integrating gender equality as both a **driver** and **outcome** of decarbonisation. Behavioural change, as shown by the IEA (2021), can reduce final energy demand but must recognise differences in access, agency and consumption patterns between men and women (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Impact of behaviour changes on final energy consumption. (Source: (IEA, 2021)).

Achieving Net Zero demands a **Just Transition**, a socially inclusive shift ensuring that workers and communities gain new opportunities while decarbonising energy. Frameworks such as the **World Resources Institute's Just Transition Work Programme** (WRI, 2024) advocate people-centred climate action, equity, and capacity-building in developing regions. However, global energy strategies often lack explicit gender or intersectional approaches to labour, policy and finance.

Energy transition pathways are interdependent and must integrate gender equality, social justice and equity to achieve credible, inclusive and sustainable Net Zero futures. Without this integration, transitions risk reproducing existing inequalities rather than transforming them. Examples of these pathways are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of Energy Transition Pathways

Pathway	Key Focus / Strategies
Renewable Energy Deployment	Scaling up solar, wind, hydro and geothermal through investment incentives, grid integration, and R&D.

Energy Efficiency & Conservation	Reducing energy use via improved technologies, design, and behavioural change.
Decentralisation & Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)	Promoting local generation and consumption through micro-grids and prosumer models.
Electrification of Transport & Heating	Replacing fossil-fuel systems with renewable electricity (EVs, heat pumps).
Hydrogen Economy	Producing and utilising green hydrogen as a clean energy carrier.
Carbon Capture, Utilisation & Storage (CCUS)	Capturing and storing CO ₂ from industry and energy sources.
Circular Economy & Resource Efficiency	Recycling, re-use and eco-design to minimise resource extraction and waste.
Social Justice & Equity	Ensuring fair access, participatory governance, and inclusion of marginalised groups in energy benefits.

These pathways are not mutually exclusive and can be combined and adapted to specific regional contexts, policy goals, and technological advancements.

Whatever pathways are followed for energy transition, these must include not only a social perspective that involves a just energy transition, but also a gender lens that will allow to improve women's participation in the generation and adoption of the pathways.

3. Backcasting and Scenario Approaches for Energy Pathway Development within the Genesys Project

Backcasting has become an influential method in sustainability studies concerned with long term systemic transformation. Its relevance for the Genesys project lies in its capacity to support the design of normative energy pathways, particularly in contexts where structural change is required to achieve social, environmental, and technological objectives. The method contrasts with conventional scenario development, although both approaches can be complementary within integrated assessment processes.

3.1 The Concept and Rationale of Backcasting

Backcasting focuses on the achievement of a desirable future state rather than the continuation of present trends. The term was introduced by Robinson and is elaborated by Dreborg, who argues that forecasting approaches are poorly suited to complex sustainability questions that require major socio technical changes rather than incremental adjustments (Dreborg, 1996). Forecasting methods typically extrapolate dominant trends and therefore struggle to generate solutions that presuppose the deliberate breaking of these trends. In contrast, backcasting begins with the definition of a normative end point and then works backwards in order to identify the policy, technological and societal changes that would be required to reach it (Dreborg, 1996; Wangel, 2011; Bibri, 2018).

Dreborg (1996) suggests that backcasting is particularly appropriate when existing systems are clearly unsustainable and when the scale of change required is so great that incremental or marginal change cannot deliver the necessary transformation. Under such circumstances, futures studies must address

discontinuities and the possibility of structural breaks. Backcasting is thus positioned as a problem-solving approach that aims to develop alternative images of the future which can inform policy formation and public debate. The differences between forecasting and backcasting according to Dreborg (1906) are indicated in table 1.

Table 2. Differences between forecasting and backcasting (Source: Dreborg, 1996).

	Forecasting	Backcasting
1. Philosophical views	Causality; determinism; context of justification	Causality & teleology; partial indeterminacy; += context of discovery
2. Perspective	Dominant trends; likely futures; possible marginal adjustments	Societal problem in need of solution; desirable futures
3. Approach	Extrapolate trends into the future; sensitivity analysis	Define interesting futures; analyse consequences and conditions for these futures to materialise
4. Methods	Various econometric models	Partial and conditional extrapolations highlighting polarities and technological limits
5. Techniques	Various mathematical algorithms	Various but not specific

Backcasting provides an opportunity to look the road ahead, as well as the tools to imagine the best possible destination. It is about imagining a very clear future not constrained by the limits of the past experience. This creates a sense of freedom and unleashes new ideas, and new possibilities. There is a rigour that once you identify the future state of possibilities then you have the tools to develop from the desired future the reasoned, creating the critical path back to your current state (Leung, 2016). Backcasting plays an important role in planning in organizations, communities and sectors. Rather than simply projecting out the current direction and accepting it as their future path, backcasting invites stakeholders to share a common goal or intention about a different future they want to “**create**” and then find new ways to achieve it (Leung, 2016).

The approach has been widely used in sustainable energy studies in Sweden and elsewhere, especially where the aim is to examine transitions that integrate technological innovation with wider behavioural, cultural and institutional shifts (Dreborg, 1996). Other applications in the Global South have included the use of backcasting for participatory transition design, for instance for electric cooking in rural Kenya to co-develop future pathways towards one hundred percent cooking with electricity by 2030 (Hivos, 2020). This exercise worked with community members to vision what cooking practices, appliances and energy services might look like in 2030, identifying key steps in behaviour, infrastructure, technology, finance and regulation that would be necessary to achieve this vision (Hivos, 2020). Backcasting here functions as a structured way to make local aspirations visible and to connect them to national policy debates on clean cooking and rural electrification.

Similarly, the European Commission guide on how to get started with the backcasting approach presents backcasting as a strategic planning technique for long term complex issues that involve multiple actors, institutions and scales (EC, 2023). It highlights the usefulness of defining a clear vision and long term aims and then identifying the pathways and milestones that can connect the current

state with the desired future. The guide emphasises that the approach is particularly suitable where countries or organisations have diverse starting points and there is no single linear or prescriptive route forward, thus reinforcing the flexibility of backcasting as a participatory and context specific tool (EC, 2023).

3.2 Scenario Approaches: Purposes and Characteristics

Differently to backcasting, scenario development constitutes a central component of integrated assessment. Scenarios are used to explore multiple plausible futures and to support understanding of causal interactions, feedback and uncertainties within complex socio ecological and socio technical systems. They are not predictions or forecasts but rather structured stories about how the future might unfold under different assumptions and driving forces (Kok, Rothman and Patel, 2006). In this sense, scenarios are designed to expand the range of possibilities considered by decision makers and stakeholders, and to provide policy relevant insights. Narrative scenarios can integrate diverse knowledge sources and scales and can inform both formal and informal decision processes.

Within the intuitive logic's tradition of scenario planning, Bradfield, Derbyshire and Wright argue for a stronger engagement with historical analysis in order to enhance causal reasoning about the future (Bradfield, Derbyshire and Wright, 2016). They caution that an exclusive focus on novelty can lead to neglect of recurring patterns, while an exclusive focus on history can constrain imagination. Their proposal is that careful use of historical cases can deepen understanding of causation and improve the quality of scenario narratives, without reducing them to simple extrapolations of the past (Bradfield, Derbyshire and Wright, 2016). The literature on scenarios construction is vast and used in multiple reports by different organisations but is not the purpose to provide a full review in this report.

3.3 Differences and Complementarities between Backcasting and Scenarios

Although backcasting and scenario approaches share an interest in long term futures and complex systems, they differ in purpose, orientation and direction of analysis. Backcasting is explicitly normative and goal oriented. It begins with a desirable future state, such as universal access to clean energy or a climate neutral energy system and works backwards to determine what would be required to reach that state (Dreborg, 1996; Bibri, 2018; Hivos, 2020; EC, 2023). The focus is thus on problem solving and on identifying strategic steps, policies and investments that can close the gap between present conditions and the normative end point.

Scenario approaches are primarily exploratory. They examine what might happen under different combinations of drivers and assumptions, and they aim to broaden perceptions of what is plausible, without necessarily endorsing any particular future as a preferred outcome (Kok, Rothman and Patel, 2006; Bradfield, Derbyshire and Wright, 2016). Scenarios can include desirable and undesirable futures and can be used to test the robustness of policies and strategies across a range of conditions.

Despite these distinctions, the two approaches may be complementary. Scenario work can provide rich contextual understanding of drivers, constraints and uncertainties, which can be used as input to backcasting exercises. Conversely, backcasting can sharpen the normative orientation of scenario processes by specifying the qualities of futures that are considered desirable and by assessing which scenarios contain pathways that can realistically lead to those futures.

3.4 Application to Energy Pathway Development in the Genesys Project

The Genesys project, with its focus on just and sustainable energy transitions, focused on backcasting to define and analyse normative energy pathways. Within Genesys, backcasting can therefore help to

convert broad long-term goals into coherent energy pathways, while scenario analysis ensures that these pathways are informed by a realistic appreciation of uncertainties, trade-offs and alternative developments. Together they support the design of robust strategies and policies that can navigate uncertainty while remaining aligned with normative commitments to social justice, gender equality and environmental integrity.

Backcasting is a powerful tool for the construction of transformative and normative energy pathways, especially where existing systems are unsustainable and incremental change is insufficient (Dreborg, 1996; EC 2023). This helps to support coherent, evidence based, and inclusive energy transition strategies. Its value for the Genesys project lies in the way it encourages participants to step outside existing constraints in order to articulate ambitious energy futures, and then to interrogate the feasibility and implications of the steps needed to realise those futures (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Backcasting for the Genesys project pathways: education and policy (Adapted from Leung, 2016).

4. Methodology

For the co-creation of the pathways all elements of the concept work of the gEneSys project and assessments conducted were considered to select the two topics of the pathways education and policy. These elements included the work conducted on education, the literature review and ontology, the survey results, the consideration of policy issues of the SHIFTS project review, the indicators selected and the Gendered Innovation Approach.

The gEneSys project organised a Workshop in Brussels on June 17th, 2025, with key stakeholders. It was designed as a collaborative exercise to co-create practical and imaginative pathways for embedding gender equality within Europe's energy transition. The event brought together participants from academia, policymaking, and other stakeholders who worked collectively to prepare a vision of energy gendered and just pathways focused on education and policy, and how they could function as complementary mechanisms for achieving long-term social and environmental goals. The event was structured as an interactive process that combined facilitated discussion, group work, and

documentation of proposals (Annex 1). It was conducted under the Chatham House Rule to encourage openness and candour in sharing ideas and reflections.

A total of 35 invitations to different stakeholders were sent and a total of 12 participants including five partners from the project attended the workshop as per table 2. The invitations were focused on policy and education as per the selected pathways for the workshop.

Table 2. Participants of the genesys workshop

Type of stakeholder	Number of participants
Academia/research organisation	5
Government organisation	7
Total	12

The Workshop was designed around a story telling exercise and a backcasting approach to participatory foresight.

The EU SHAPENERGY project developed a guide on the use of storytelling in energy transition contexts, which offers multiple examples of why and how this method can be used to bring multiple but mainly end-user voices into problem solving, and to support interdisciplinary learning on renewable energy (Mourik et al, 2017).

In gEneSys, the goal is to improve the engagement of women in energy transition, not as end-users but as researchers, innovators, and policy makers. The storytelling approach is helpful in this context and can be framed by adapting guiding questions from Mourik and Rothman (2013). The aim of the storytelling would be to help understand personal perspectives on how to advance professionally in energy transition sector. The example questions used were:

- How am I motivated to respond, or change my interests?
- Why should I do this?
- What do I need to do and what others do?
- What will it take or what will it 'cost' me to change my career direction?
- Will I get help?
- What do I need to do to make progress in my career?
- How much will I need to change to be accepted as a professional in the field?

The storytelling approach was used to help enhance the results obtained as part of the workshop to add depth and nuance on how the educational and policy energy transition pathways could be made more responsive to the professional interests of women already in or thinking of making a transition into the energy sector.

The workshop used backcasting as a planning and analytical method that begins with the identification of a desired future and works backwards to determine the actions and enabling conditions required to achieve it. Unlike forecasting, which projects current trends forward, backcasting invites participants to imagine alternative futures and to design pathways that make those futures attainable. This

Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology

approach is particularly suited to complex socio-technical transitions such as the move towards a gender-just energy system, where change depends not only on technology but also on values, institutions, and social behaviour.

At the outset, participants agreed upon a shared 2050 vision: *a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy*. This vision served as the fixed point of reference for all subsequent discussions. Working backwards from this vision, participants identified milestones for 2035 and 2025, specifying the actions, institutional changes, and cultural shifts required to reach the desired future.

The two main thematic pathways education and policy were presented as interdependent systems through which gender equality in the energy transition could be realised. Within each pathway, participants identified practical actions, structural reforms, and cross-cutting mechanisms such as data, funding, and representation. The education pathway focused on awareness-raising, access, interdisciplinarity, and cultural transformation within teaching and research institutions. The policy pathway centred on governance, data infrastructure, financial instruments, and participatory mechanisms that institutionalise equality.

Throughout the workshop, the facilitation team guided participants through a sequence of collaborative exercises. These included the articulation of near-term actions (2025), the projection of medium-term developments (2035), and the analysis of how these stages interconnect to achieve the 2050 vision. Notes, post-it stickers and plenary contributions were documented and consolidated into a set of written outcomes. These records, together with the workshop transcript, form the empirical foundation of this report (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Vision, pathways, actions and mechanisms identified by participants (June 17th, 2025).

The backcasting method proved effective in linking imagination with practicality. It encouraged participants to think beyond immediate constraints while remaining grounded in feasible steps. It also revealed the interconnectedness of education and policy, showing how reforms in one domain support progress in the other. By combining individual insight with collective reasoning, the method enabled the co-creation of a shared framework of action that moves from awareness and preparation to integration and normalisation.

In methodological terms, the workshop exemplified how participatory foresight can be applied to policy design and knowledge co-production. It demonstrated that envisioning desirable futures through dialogue not only clarifies objectives but also fosters ownership among stakeholders. The process transformed abstract concepts of gender justice and energy transition into a tangible roadmap that connects social inclusion, institutional reform, and sustainability within a coherent temporal structure.

5. Storytelling representative comments

Participant A

I work in the field of regulation. We have research policy events and trainings in energy and climate regulation. I mainly work in energy. Within the school, we have a gender mainstreaming initiative which originated as a grassroots initiative. It was mostly internal at first because we saw that there are fewer women participating in the courses. We saw that we wanted to create more equitable practises where we have more women speaking at our events, participating in our trainings, etc. We started offering scholarships for our training courses to women from all over the world at any stage of their career. Those who think that they need to attend a course for upscaling, rescaling, etc. We have an application process, and we select the recipients each year. We also have the energy talent database for women professionals in the energy sector where they can create a profile. If somebody is looking for a new hire, if they're looking for a co-author for their paper, for a speaker, they can consult this database and find a suitable person. Another initiative to promote professionals is the Luce Awards programme, which recognises achievements of women in the green transition field. There are two awards: one for a long-standing career, and another for early-stage careers. For instance, this year, one

of the winners in the emerging talent category was a woman who created an upcycling textile organisation in Tanzania into bags and garments, to battle against textile waste. In addition, we promote professional women using social media letting women write a blog about their expertise. We record interviews with already established professionals in the energy sector to inspire other women to go into the energy sector. With this initiative, we want to promote just energy transition through empowering women to join the sector, maybe upscale and elevate their careers, etc. I would advise women to really speak up and to raise their voice and be confident about whatever they want to say, either if it's their opinion during class about a topic or about a presentation, for example, of a research topic they were working on.

Participant B

My background is international politics. I concluded my Masters' degree in November and then I came to Brussels. I live in a city in the Veneto region in Italy. Having the possibility to work with EU stakeholders and policy makers to conclude the student's path is highly valued. The Veneto region council [is] involved in energy projects. They are really focussing on hydrogen right now. And we studied a little bit the eco-design rules because they are impacting several aspects of our everyday life. The Veneto region is one of the biggest industrial regions in Italy. So, the industrial point of view dominates discussions on what actions are needed to have a better future. We have to take notice of all the points that can give advantage to Veneto citizens. I really want to work in the energy sector because it's a tangible sector where I can work for the future. With an international politics background, I am trying to be an expert on understanding political risks in achieving the green vision. Currently, the political agenda of energy transition is being reshaped by wars, and the conditions we took for granted in the past have been destroyed. There were always people who believed that basically climate change does not exist, and we can live as we want, and we can't stop reliance on oil because of aeroplanes and so on. I think they are using these political arguments to say basically that there are more important things, and I suspect it might be just the same people who will argue against energy transition and spending more on defence. These are easy arguments to make to scare people of green future. My Master's was not focused on energy. It was mainly concerned about law, history, economy, but not energy. I know that my university has Masters' that are focused on energy transition and the human rights departments. Maybe that is the correct way to move forward.

Participant C

The course I am doing is on *energy.....*, so you would expect that there is the part about sustainability and future, but it is an intensely engineering course. We had two economists who applied by accident and were surprised by the high amount of the engineering content. We have not had any mentions of gender issues, we have had no social justice modules, we have had nothing on any justice except one energy justice lecture. We could have had guest lectures from different people from different industries. The course is essentially defined as having technological core, with focus on nuclear, solar and wind but not social aspects. When I was looking at Master courses, I did notice that Germany had more varied courses, in terms of involvement of policy, it was not just hardcore sciences. Maybe this is also my fault as an engineer, I was thinking that this is my expertise, so I would be more happy in my current course, but now that I am doing my thesis, which I am doing with Philosophy, I think I should have done my Master's in Germany.

6. Framing the Vision and Pathways

At the heart of the workshop was a shared 2050 vision: *a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy*. This statement captured a comprehensive ambition that unites

sustainability with justice, emphasising that the energy transition must not only decarbonise systems but also democratise access, participation, and opportunity. To give substance to this vision, participants used a backcasting methodology to identify the necessary conditions, policies, and educational measures for 2035 and 2025. Working backwards allowed them to explore the sequence of actions and decisions required to reach the desired future, anchoring the vision in feasible, time-bound steps.

The workshop was based on the recognition that energy transitions are social as well as technological transformations. Participants conceptualised gender-just energy transitions as processes of societal reorganisation that reshape power relations, redistribute opportunities, and diversify the production of knowledge. In their discussions, gender equality was not framed as an outcome to be added at the end of a technological process, but as a principle that should guide innovation, governance, and participation from the outset (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Energy pathways focus and Vision.

Education and policy were established as the two central pathways for the backcasting exercise. Education was identified as the arena where knowledge, awareness, and values are formed, while policy was recognised as the structure through which these values become embedded in institutional practice. Participants worked within these two pathways to define short- and medium-term actions, highlighting their interdependence and complementarity.

Throughout the workshop, three cross-cutting priorities emerged as essential to both pathways. The first was interdisciplinarity, viewed as the means to connect technological expertise with social understanding and to promote inclusive problem-solving. The second was data transparency, considered indispensable for accountability and informed decision-making. The third was the dismantling of structural barriers that perpetuate inequality in access to education, employment, and governance. Together, these priorities provided the conceptual bridge between immediate action and long-term transformation.

The framing discussions that opened the workshop established a shared understanding of purpose: to translate the 2050 vision into actionable pathways that integrate gender, sustainability, and innovation. The process was participatory and iterative, combining individual reflection with group synthesis. The result was a coherent set of linked actions across education and policy that illustrate how Europe can move from awareness and preparation in 2025, to institutional consolidation in 2035, and finally to systemic normalisation by 2050 (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Framing of Genesys vision for 2050.

7. Education in 2025: Building Awareness and Inclusion

7.1 2025 Vision

The 2025 vision for education reflected a shared determination to build the intellectual, cultural, and institutional foundations for a gender-aware energy transition. Within the backcasting exercise, participants regarded education as the social system through which ideas of fairness, participation, and sustainability could take hold. This first stage was therefore not about reaching immediate parity but about preparing the structures of knowledge and awareness necessary for long-term transformation.

Participants identified **education** as a pathway where the links between gender, technology, and society could be made visible. One participant underlined its importance by saying that *“education and policy, even though they are not so mentioned and clustered within the research field, are super important.”* This recognition captured the spirit of 2025 as a preparatory period, one devoted to designing curricula, fostering awareness, and equipping future generations to see energy as a social as well as a technological issue.

The group discussed the need to reform how energy is taught in schools and universities. A participant observed that *“there is a general lack of gender perspective in the energy education. Usually, energy jobs are portrayed as male dominated... and basically nothing on the gender education.”* This pointed to an enduring structural gap: energy education had long been disconnected from questions of social justice and equality. Written proposals such as *“Introduce compulsory classes on energy and social aspects: gender equality, energy poverty, etc. in schools and universities”* and *“High school curricula on renewable energy with female role models”* demonstrated their ambition to address this gap through curricular innovation and representation.

Equally central was the idea of awareness and advocacy. Participants understood that changes in teaching must be accompanied by shifts in public discourse. As one participant insisted, *“Now we have a vision, so what we can start today is everything which is linked to advocacy and communication at large. So, awareness campaigns, coalition building, speak to policy makers.”* The same emphasis appeared in the written notes calling for *“Advocacy actions: awareness campaigns; coalition building; joint statements.”* In the context of backcasting, these ideas functioned as near-term actions capable of creating the social legitimacy and public visibility required for more substantial reforms by 2035.

Participants also called for concrete steps to expand women’s access to education and employment in the energy sector. Written proposals included *“create upskilling and reskilling courses for the clean transition with particular focus on women (through scholarships, etc.)”* and *“make quotas on gender for higher education programmes mandatory including energy courses.”* This linked gender equality directly to the clean energy transition, making inclusion a condition for technological progress rather than a secondary concern. One participant warned against superficial compliance, stating that *“just saying how many students are enrolled is not enough. We need to move away from just giving those that you are covering gender because you think that you have 50 and 50, which is not really true.”*

Another important theme was interdisciplinarity. The participants saw education as an integrative force connecting policy, science, and society. As one participant explained, *“education is not just for the technological side and the social side on gender, but also for policy... how are people who are in policy prepared to really do that, if they are not fully aware and really more educated onto these aspects.”* Another participant shared a personal insight from teaching experience: *“I teach sustainability, and I see that the female students are very much interested when you do it in that way. If it is just a hardcore chemistry, they don’t like it at all. But this is the old way, and so we need now this.”* Together, these statements highlighted that inclusive and interdisciplinary teaching attracts diverse learners and builds the capacity for systemic thinking essential to the energy transition.

In the logic of the backcasting exercise, these 2025 actions were conceived as preparatory and catalytic. They aimed to transform education from a neutral conduit of technical knowledge into a creative and reflective process that fosters equality, awareness, and participation. This stage represented the “awareness and foundation” phase of the long-term pathway toward the 2050 vision of a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy.

7.2 Education in 2035: Institutionalisation and Cultural Transformation

By 2035, participants envisioned education as an institutional driver of equality rather than a site of incremental change. The focus moved from awareness-raising to embedding gender considerations into the daily functioning of academic and training systems. Within the logic of the backcasting exercise, this represented the consolidation phase: the point at which cultural change begun in 2025 becomes structural and self-reinforcing.

Participants viewed this future as one in which interdisciplinarity, visibility, and data-driven transparency define the educational landscape. The backcasting notes contained repeated calls for *“Interdisciplinarity embedded in higher education programmes”* and *“Experiment with interdisciplinarity.”* These proposals recognised that connecting technological, environmental, and social knowledge was essential for achieving the broader 2050 vision. As one participant observed, *“we need systemic integration in the future, so it means... women are really attracted by interconnections, by integration, and so this is really an opportunity for women to be involved in this*

future energy transition system.” Their reasoning linked interdisciplinarity directly to gender inclusion, suggesting that systemic thinking naturally expands the space for participation.

Representation and leadership were also central themes in the 2035 vision. Participants argued that visibility is inseparable from structural equality. Written actions included *“Assigning prizes and awards to female students attending energy courses in universities”* and *“More women working in higher education on energy (lecturers).”* One participant reflected on the deeper meaning of such measures, explaining that *“symbols are very, very important... when you get to define a structure, so everything goes with it.”* This remark captured how recognition and role models can reshape the internal culture of academic institutions, reinforcing inclusion as both practice and symbol.

The 2035 horizon also aimed to erase the cultural stigma surrounding energy and engineering disciplines. One participant drew attention to how teaching methods can either reinforce or dismantle stereotypes: *“I teach sustainability, and I see that the female students are very much interested when you do it in that way. If it is just a hardcore chemistry, they don’t like it at all. But this is the old way, and so we need now this.”* The group agreed that energy education should embrace social relevance, sustainability, and creativity, values that attract broader participation and reflect a new cultural identity for the sector.

Knowledge-sharing and transparency were another defining concern. The participants proposed *“Open access to cross-sectional gender disaggregated data on energy access, participation and consumption”* and *“Research publishers create journals that connect policy and education on sustainable energy transition.”* This emphasis aligned with their earlier insistence that reliable data is indispensable for measuring progress and informing future decisions. The educational system of 2035 was therefore imagined as both a producer and a steward of data, ensuring that equality remains evidence-based and accountable.

Finally, participants emphasised that education must operate in close partnership with policy and industry. The notes reflected this integrated approach through references to *“research publishers connecting policy and education”* and discussions linking academia to policymaking. Education was described as the bridge between knowledge and governance, enabling evidence to travel across institutions and influencing how energy transitions are managed and understood.

Taken together, the 2035 actions describe an education system that has internalised gender equality as a structural norm. Interdisciplinarity, representation, and openness were not seen as optional innovations but as defining characteristics of a sustainable learning culture. This stage represented the institutional consolidation of the equality principles imagined for 2025 and laid the cultural and intellectual groundwork for achieving the 2050 vision of a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy.

8. Policy in 2025: Governance Foundations and Visibility

8.1 Policy 2025

The 2025 vision for policy was conceived as a decisive turning point in which equality in energy governance begins to take shape through evidence, regulation, and institutional reform. During the backcasting discussions, participants positioned policy as the framework that could translate awareness and advocacy into measurable and enforceable action. They agreed that the first step towards the 2050 vision of *“a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy”* required rebuilding policy foundations to make gender equality both visible and operational.

A recurring theme was the lack of reliable data and the absence of coherent structures for monitoring progress. One participant explained that *“we have quite a general lack of data. But actually, there are usually a bunch of data out there... Many of them are produced in a more or less systematic way by project... Many of them collect data, so it's important to take stock of this data and of this project.”* The group considered this absence of systematic evidence to be one of the biggest obstacles to informed policymaking. Written actions reflected the same concern, calling for *“Establish a framework to collect disaggregated data”* and *“Start collecting data that is intersectional, and gender disaggregated in Europe and beyond.”* Another participant added that *“we keep the idea of the monitoring... I also put, for example, creating a framework for the database collection, because it is too much to say, oh, we need disaggregated data. Yeah, but how?”* This exchange illustrated the group's conviction that data collection must move from rhetorical demand to structured implementation.

Participants also discussed how policies and corporate practices must embed equality as a requirement rather than an option. Several written actions captured this institutional emphasis: *“Guidelines for gender and energy for policy-makers and industry”* and *“Management training on gender issues in companies.”* One participant argued that *“we need to produce a guideline on gender and energy that can be really distributed to policymakers and to industry.”* Another key proposal was the introduction of *“National policy to make mandatory for energy companies to fund mentorship for women mainstreaming into the energy sector.”* These ideas positioned inclusion not as symbolic but as legally and financially grounded.

Funding was regarded as both a driver and a test of commitment. Participants insisted that *“funding to have a clear and cross-cutting gender earmarking”* was essential for progress, linking this to a broader recognition that *“there is nothing we can do if it is not changed. This is from the policy point of view.”* In their view, equitable financing represented the tangible translation of principles into practice.

Finally, participants emphasised that policy transformation in 2025 required visibility and advocacy to secure political will. As one contributor stated, *“Now we have a vision, so what we can start today is everything which is linked to advocacy and communication at large. So, awareness campaigns, coalition building, speak to policy makers.”* The written notes reiterated this ambition through calls to *“Bring energy equality to the front of EU and national policymaking”* and *“Speak to policymakers.”* Advocacy was seen as a method of embedding equality within the public consciousness and ensuring accountability among institutions.

Taken together, these reflections portray 2025 as a foundational stage for restructuring energy governance. It was not imagined as a time of full achievement but as one of institutional creation, where data systems, gender frameworks, funding instruments, and advocacy networks are established to support future integration. In the logic of the backcasting process, this moment laid the groundwork for the systemic alignment and cultural transformation envisioned for 2035 and ultimately for the 2050 goal of sustainable, inclusive energy access.

8.2 Policy in 2035: Systemic Integration and Cultural Consolidation

The 2035 vision for policy described an institutional environment where gender equality had moved from principle to practice, becoming a defining feature of governance and organisational culture. Building on the structural groundwork of 2025, participants envisioned policies that operate as dynamic systems, constantly monitored, integrated across sectors, and co-produced with citizens. In the backcasting logic, this stage represented consolidation and integration, the point where institutional reforms begin to generate measurable social change and durable cultural transformation.

Participants agreed that equality must be sustained through binding measures and continuous oversight. The backcasting outcomes identified *“quotas for industry on energy jobs at all levels”* and *“financial instruments; education instruments; monitoring instruments; policy and plans.”* These tools were designed to formalise gender balance and to evaluate progress over time. The emphasis on consistent evidence and review echoed one participant’s insistence that *“periodical impact assessments or the feasibility of a policy... I’m a big fan of data and policymaking by data.”* For participants, regulation and data collection were twin mechanisms that made equality both enforceable and traceable.

Cultural transformation was considered equally important. Participants reflected on the enduring legacies of older institutional models, observing that *“perhaps also both the educational and the policy system were designed and thought back in the day more from a male perspective... so siloed or with all disciplines very vertical. So now to rethink the structure is really fundamental to think about the change.”* The written outcomes for 2035 reinforced this ambition through calls for *“cultural shifts, more integration, agenda setting and framing.”* The shift from gender awareness to gender-conscious governance was thus presented as both an ethical and structural reform.

Intersectionality was a defining feature of the 2035 vision. The written actions proposed *“subsidies in relation to renewable energy having intersectional criteria, meaning female-led households affected by energy poverty are one of the recipients”* and *“policies favouring awareness raising on dedicated funding and opportunities for women in energy efficiency and access.”* Another participant connected this theme directly to justice and inclusion, noting the importance of *“reduction of energy poverty, particularly focusing on distributional implications on women due to potential high and volatile energy prices.”* These actions framed energy access as a social right tied to equality and economic security.

Empowerment and participation were also central. Participants wanted policies that allow women and youth to influence decisions rather than merely benefit from them. The group proposed *“mechanisms that empower youth, and especially women, to influence energy policy and regulation”* and *“more active participation of men in matters related to gender equality in the energy sector.”* This reflected a belief that inclusion depends on shared responsibility and that long-term change must involve all genders in shaping governance.

Finally, the group stressed that achieving integration requires dismantling silos between different policy domains. One participant explained that *“policy is conducted in silos... when you de-silo policies, actually this can have this effect, this unintended effect to attract more women also... it just becomes more inclusive.”* This echoed the broader call for *“more integration, agenda setting and framing”* found in the written outcomes. Integration was not simply administrative coordination but a rethinking of how systems relate, connecting education, energy, finance, and industry under a common commitment to equality.

In this 2035 vision, gender equality becomes a structural norm supported by regulation, cultural change, and participatory mechanisms. Policy is no longer reactive but proactive, constantly learning from data, experience, and citizen engagement. This phase marked the realisation of a mature, inclusive governance culture capable of sustaining the 2050 vision of a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy.

9. Overlaps, Intersections, and Pathway Synergies

The backcasting process revealed that the education and policy pathways are deeply interwoven, functioning as parallel structures in the pursuit of the 2050 vision of *“a sustainable society supported*

by equal and inclusive access to clean energy.” Participants consistently acknowledged that change in one domain reinforces and accelerates progress in the other. Education was seen as the space where values and competencies are formed, while policy was viewed as the arena where those values become institutional practice. Their discussions highlighted that neither pathway can succeed in isolation; both are sustained through shared mechanisms of knowledge, visibility, and accountability.

9.1 Intersectional Data as a Common Foundation

Participants across both education and policy discussions identified data as the foundation upon which equality in the energy transition must rest. The recurring theme throughout the backcasting process was that without evidence, neither progress nor accountability can be secured. Data was therefore understood not merely as information but as an instrument of fairness, allowing policy and education to work in alignment and to learn from one another.

Several participants reflected on the limitations of current approaches to gender and energy data. As indicated in section 7, one participant indicated *“we have quite a general lack of data. But actually, there are usually a bunch of data out there. Many of them are produced in a more or less systematic way by project. Many of them collect data, so it's important to take stock of this data and of this project.”* This observation revealed a collective frustration: knowledge about gender and energy exists in fragments but remains uncoordinated, poorly shared, and underutilised. Participants interpreted this as both a technical and a political challenge. Without systematic data collection, gender continues to be treated as an assumption rather than a measurable dimension of policy and practice.

As indicated in section 7.1, another participant underlined that action must replace general appeals for data collection with the statement *“we keep the idea of the monitoring. I also put, for example, creating a framework for the database collection, because it is too much to say, oh, we need disaggregated data. Yeah, but how?”* This comment reflected a crucial methodological insight: data systems must be purposefully designed, adequately funded, and maintained through clear institutional mandates. In the context of backcasting, participants saw 2025 as the point to establish such frameworks and 2035 as the moment to make them fully operational.

The written outcomes reinforced this vision, specifying the need for *“Open access to cross-sectional gender disaggregated data on energy access, participation and consumption.”* This statement connected data transparency with democratic values and the right to information. Participants agreed that shared access to gender-disaggregated data would not only enhance accountability but also support education and research by revealing inequalities that are currently hidden. Open data was therefore conceived as both a governance tool and an educational resource.

Participants also emphasised that data must be intersectional, capturing how gender interacts with income, geography, ethnicity, and social class. This insistence on intersectionality reflected an awareness that equality cannot be measured through single categories. Participants believed that understanding differences within groups is essential to designing inclusive policies and educational strategies.

In the broader framework of the 2050 vision, the insistence on data represents the desire for a culture of evidence and transparency to underpin equality. Through data, participants sought to connect the everyday realities of citizens with the institutional mechanisms that shape their access to energy, learning, and opportunity. Reliable, open, and intersectional data was seen as the connective tissue binding together education, policy, and justice, enabling informed action across all levels of governance and society.

9.2 Interdisciplinarity and Policy Integration

Interdisciplinarity and policy integration emerged during the backcasting exercise as central mechanisms for achieving the 2050 vision of a sustainable and inclusive energy society. Participants regarded the separation of academic disciplines and policy domains as one of the most persistent obstacles to equality in the energy transition. They argued that genuine transformation depends on connecting the social, technological, and institutional dimensions of knowledge and decision-making.

Participants repeatedly noted that fragmented approaches hinder both innovation and participation. As indicated in section 7.2, one participant explained that *“policy is conducted in silos. When you de-silo policies, actually this can have this effect, this unintended effect to attract more women also. It just becomes more inclusive.”* This comment captured the belief that integration does more than improve efficiency; it reshapes how inclusivity is produced within institutions. Removing silos, in their view, is not only about coordination but also about redefining values, incentives, and outcomes so that the system itself becomes open to diversity.

The written outcomes of the backcasting activity reinforced this idea, calling for *“more integration, agenda setting and framing.”* Participants interpreted this as a long-term commitment to institutional learning. Integration was described as a practice that requires communication across ministries, sectors, and disciplines. In education, interdisciplinarity was seen as a mirror to this process, nurturing the cognitive skills needed to connect scientific, economic, and social perspectives. In policy, integration was viewed as the structural equivalent of that intellectual openness, ensuring that ideas developed in education translate into action in governance.

The discussion revealed a strong connection between interdisciplinary learning and gender inclusion. Several participants associated women’s participation with integrative thinking and collaboration. As one participant put it (see section 7.2), *“we need systemic integration in the future, so it means women are really attracted by interconnections, by integration, and so this is really an opportunity for women to be involved in this future energy transition system.”* This comment linked inclusivity with creativity, suggesting that diverse perspectives thrive in environments that encourage connection rather than competition.

Participants also highlighted that interdisciplinarity promotes accountability because it allows for shared responsibility between actors. When educators, researchers, and policymakers communicate across boundaries, each becomes aware of the social consequences of their work. Integration, therefore, was not simply a structural reform but an ethical stance, embedding cooperation and dialogue as defining principles of governance and education alike.

By 2035, participants envisioned a Europe where interdisciplinary education and integrated policy are inseparable. This would be a context in which teaching, research, and regulation are mutually informed and sustained by shared objectives of equality and sustainability. In this way, interdisciplinarity and policy integration were seen as two expressions of the same idea: that inclusive transitions depend on breaking barriers between people, institutions, and fields of knowledge.

9.3 Gender Visibility and Representation

Gender visibility and representation were identified by participants as essential drivers of equality across both the education and policy pathways. Visibility was understood as the means through which recognition, legitimacy, and participation are achieved. The discussions during the backcasting exercise

revealed a shared understanding that representation operates on two levels: as a practical necessity to ensure fairness and as a symbolic force that changes how society perceives authority and belonging.

In education, participants argued that representation begins with visibility in curricula and leadership. The written outcomes as in section 6.2 proposed *“Assigning prizes and awards to female students attending energy courses in universities”* and *“More women working in higher education on energy (lecturers).”* These actions were designed to correct the absence of women from key academic roles and to show students that leadership in science and technology can take diverse forms. One participant articulated the symbolic dimension of such visibility by stating that *“symbols are very, very important. When you get to define a structure, so everything goes with it.”* This remark illustrated the group’s conviction that the structures of education mirror the values of society, and that visible female role models help redefine institutional and cultural expectations.

Within policy, visibility was framed as an instrument of inclusion and accountability. The written actions (section 6.1) included *“National policy to make mandatory for energy companies to fund mentorship for women mainstreaming into the energy sector”* and *“Guidelines for gender and energy for policy-makers and industry.”* Participants believed that these forms of representation within governance and industry signal legitimacy and create pathways for wider participation. Visible women in leadership positions demonstrate that gender equality is not only a moral issue but also a requirement for good governance and sound decision-making.

Participants further observed that representation must extend beyond numbers to encompass power and influence. One participant cautioned that *“just saying how many students are enrolled is not enough. We need to move away from just giving those that you are covering gender because you think that you have 50 and 50, which is not really true.”* This insight drew attention to the distinction between participation and meaningful representation, underscoring the need to assess who holds authority, not just who is present.

The backcasting logic placed representation at the intersection of education and policy because it enables learning and decision-making to reflect the diversity of experience in society. Participants linked this to the 2050 vision by stressing that equality must be visible in the public sphere before it can become embedded in structures. Representation, in their words, is both evidence and promise: evidence of progress and promise of a fairer system. By ensuring visibility in classrooms, boardrooms, and government institutions, participants envisioned a Europe where the presence of women in energy and governance would be ordinary, recognised, and unremarkable, signifying that equality had become part of the social fabric.

9.4 Cultural and Institutional Transformation

Cultural and institutional transformation was regarded by participants as one of the most challenging yet necessary conditions for achieving the 2050 vision of a sustainable and inclusive energy society. Throughout the backcasting discussions, participants repeatedly emphasised that equality cannot be achieved through technical reform alone. The underlying cultural norms that shape institutions, policies, and everyday practices must also evolve. Culture, in this sense, was described as the unseen structure that either supports or undermines change.

Participants recognised that both education and policy systems have inherited frameworks built on traditional assumptions that no longer serve an inclusive agenda. In section 7.2, one participant observed that *“perhaps also both the educational and the policy system were designed and thought back in the day more from a male perspective. So siloed or with all disciplines very vertical. So now to*

rethink the structure is really fundamental to think about the change.” This reflection encapsulated the need to examine the historical foundations of governance and learning systems that perpetuate exclusion. For participants, cultural transformation required confronting those legacies and redesigning institutional models around cooperation, equity, and diversity.

The written outcomes of the backcasting exercise expressed this aspiration through actions such as *“cultural shifts, more integration, agenda setting and framing.”* These goals aimed to make culture itself a focus of policy and educational reform. Participants linked this to their experiences of how gender often remains marginalised in technical fields. One participant stated that *“there is a general lack of gender perspective in the energy education. Usually, energy jobs are portrayed as male dominated.”* For them, cultural transformation begins when these narratives change and when institutions recognise that diversity is integral to excellence.

Cultural change was also seen as an ongoing process that requires active participation from all levels of society. Participants discussed how language, leadership, and decision-making practices shape institutional behaviour. When education introduces equality as a central theme and policy provides frameworks that reward inclusive practices, culture begins to shift from within. Participants emphasised that these changes are mutually reinforcing: inclusive education cultivates awareness, while inclusive policy creates incentives that sustain it.

In the broader logic of backcasting, 2025 was the moment to raise consciousness and initiate dialogue, and 2035 the time to consolidate new norms. By 2050, participants imagined institutions that no longer need to justify gender equality because it has become an accepted standard of professionalism and fairness. Cultural and institutional transformation was therefore seen not as a final step but as a continuous process of renewal, ensuring that equality remains embedded in the evolving fabric of European education, governance, and society.

9.5 Economic Instruments and Incentives

Participants in the backcasting workshop regarded economic instruments and financial incentives as essential mechanisms for embedding gender equality within the structures of both education and policy. They understood that without dedicated resources, the ambitions of inclusion risk remaining symbolic. Economic tools were therefore conceived as tangible expressions of institutional commitment, capable of transforming equality from a moral aspiration into a measurable practice.

The written outcomes of the workshop highlighted this priority clearly, proposing *“Funding to have a clear and cross-cutting gender earmarking”* and *“Start-ups on policy-gender-energy linked to industry.”* These actions reflected a consensus that financial design must reflect social priorities. Funding, in the participants’ view, represents a form of policy language through which institutions communicate what truly matters. One participant emphasised this connection between finance and change by stating that *“I think this is really critical. Because there is nothing we can do if it is not changed. This is from the policy point of view.”* The remark revealed the recognition that budgets are moral documents, and that without structural reform in resource allocation, equality remains aspirational rather than operational.

In education, participants linked economic measures directly to access and empowerment. The written actions proposed *“create upskilling and reskilling courses for the clean transition with particular focus on women (through scholarships, etc.)”* and *“make quotas on gender for higher education programmes mandatory including energy courses.”* These initiatives addressed the need to remove financial barriers that prevent women from entering or remaining in the energy sector. Participants viewed such

measures as investments in talent rather than as subsidies, connecting them to the larger goal of ensuring that Europe's clean energy transition benefits from the widest possible pool of expertise.

Participants also discussed how financial instruments could stimulate innovation and bridge the gap between academia, industry, and policy. By linking gender-sensitive funding to research and start-up initiatives, they sought to create ecosystems where inclusion drives creativity and competitiveness. Incentives for mentorship, childcare support, and flexible work arrangements were seen as necessary complements to scholarships and grants. Together these measures represented an effort to redesign financial systems around human development and equality rather than around efficiency alone.

The economic dimension of equality also extended to accountability. Participants understood that financial transparency and monitoring are indispensable for ensuring that gender earmarks are not lost within larger budgets. They connected this to the broader emphasis on data, calling for tracking mechanisms that reveal where funding is directed and what impacts it produces. This emphasis on evidence reflected the belief that equality must be demonstrable and that accountability strengthens public trust.

In the long-term perspective of the backcasting exercise, economic instruments were the enablers of all other actions. They allowed educational and policy frameworks to be implemented, sustained, and adapted. By 2050, participants envisioned a system where funding for equality would no longer require justification because it would have become embedded in standard operating procedures. In this sense, financial incentives were not only tools for redistribution but also catalysts for cultural change, ensuring that the pursuit of inclusive and sustainable energy transitions is backed by durable material support.

10. Synthesis: Pathways Towards the 2050 Vision

The backcasting exercise culminated in a collective articulation of a long-term aspiration: *“a sustainable society supported by equal and inclusive access to clean energy.”* This shared 2050 vision expressed a conviction that the success of the energy transition depends not only on technological progress but also on the social and cultural conditions that shape access, knowledge, and participation. Participants worked backwards from this vision to design the milestones of 2025 and 2035, identifying the mechanisms that could make equality an integral and permanent feature of Europe's energy future.

Throughout the workshop, participants stressed that education and policy must develop together as mutually reinforcing systems. One participant summarised this interdependence by saying that *“education and policy, even though they are not so mentioned and clustered within the research field, are super important.”* Education was understood as the foundation for awareness and capability, while policy was seen as the structure that translates awareness into governance and accountability. The two pathways therefore represented different dimensions of the same transformative process.

The 2025 actions were designed to establish the enabling conditions for change. These included *“advocacy and communication at large,” “establishing frameworks for data collection,”* and *“funding to have a clear and cross-cutting gender earmarking.”* Together they laid the groundwork for participation, transparency, and institutional reform. The early stage was described by participants as an awakening period, one in which gender equality becomes a visible and legitimate subject of education and policy debate.

By 2035, participants envisioned a phase of consolidation and integration. The written actions such as *“interdisciplinarity embedded in higher education programmes,” “quotas for industry on energy jobs at all levels,”* and *“mechanisms that empower youth and especially women to influence energy policy and regulation”* reflected a shift from awareness to implementation. This middle stage represented a turning point where structural changes were expected to become self-sustaining, reinforced by cultural shifts and institutional maturity.

Across all discussions, integration emerged as a defining principle where policies need to be de-siloed to make it more inclusive. In education, participants described similar processes of connection through *“systemic integration”* and *“open systems for talent to think out of the box towards the future.”* Integration was thus understood as the mechanism through which gender equality becomes normalised, linking individual opportunity to collective progress.

Cultural transformation also occupied a central place in the synthesis. One participant reflected that *“to rethink the structure is really fundamental to think about the change.”* This statement encapsulated the idea that lasting equality requires not only institutional reform but also a change in values, attitudes, and expectations. Participants connected this ethical dimension to the idea of representation, arguing that visibility, recognition, and fairness in everyday practice are the true indicators of transformation.

In its entirety, the synthesis of the backcasting exercise reveals a coherent, stepwise pathway. The participants’ design moves from awareness and preparation in 2025, through structural consolidation and integration in 2035, to full normalisation by 2050. Each phase builds upon the previous one, combining evidence, education, governance, and culture into a self-reinforcing system. The vision they co-created portrays a Europe where equality in energy access and participation is no longer a policy objective to be pursued but a lived reality that sustains a truly sustainable society.

11. Summary of Key Recommendations for Action between 2025 and 2035

The backcasting exercise identified a clear sequence of actions required to move from early groundwork in 2025 to the full institutionalisation of equality by 2035. These actions, though distinct across education and policy, are interconnected and cumulative.

1. Strengthen gender-responsive education systems. By 2025, education systems should embed gender equality and sustainability throughout school and university curricula. Teaching should link technological knowledge with social and ethical understanding, introducing compulsory learning on energy, equality, and climate issues. By 2035, these reforms should mature into integrated interdisciplinary programmes, producing graduates capable of connecting science, policy, and society.

2. Expand women’s access, participation, and leadership. Between 2025 and 2035, targeted programmes for upskilling, reskilling, and scholarships are essential to increase women’s participation in the clean energy transition. These should be supported by flexible learning conditions and clear progression routes. By 2035, women’s representation in teaching, research, and leadership roles in higher education and industry should become the norm rather than the exception.

3. Create transparent, intersectional data systems. By 2025, frameworks for collecting gender-disaggregated and intersectional data on education, employment, and energy access must be established. By 2035, open and accessible data should inform policy, research, and monitoring at

national and European levels. Reliable data will enable the measurement of progress, strengthen accountability, and support cross-sectoral learning.

4. Institutionalise gender equality within policy and governance. Governments and regulatory bodies should embed equality into national and EU energy frameworks by 2025, including guidelines, mentorship requirements, and gender-focused funding. By 2035, equality provisions should be fully operational, enforced through quotas, monitoring mechanisms, and regular impact assessments.

5. Foster cultural transformation and social awareness. Between 2025 and 2035, advocacy and communication campaigns should be used to normalise gender equality in the energy transition. Education and policy must work together to dismantle stereotypes and to create visible, credible role models. Cultural transformation should be treated as an ongoing process, reinforced by language, leadership, and everyday practice.

6. Align financial instruments with inclusion and innovation. Financial frameworks should allocate dedicated funding for gender equality and intersectional initiatives. Between 2025 and 2035, gender-responsive budgeting, scholarships, mentorship funding, and industry incentives should become standard practice. These investments should support both equality and innovation, demonstrating that inclusion strengthens economic performance.

7. Promote participatory and inclusive decision-making. By 2035, mechanisms that empower women and youth to participate in energy governance should be established. This includes public consultations, advisory roles, and collaborative policy processes. Inclusive participation ensures that energy transitions reflect the experiences and needs of all citizens.

Together, these actions trace a pathway of continuity and reinforcement. The decade between 2025 and 2035 should transform awareness into structure, structure into culture, and culture into a lasting system of equality within Europe’s clean energy transition (Figure 1).

Figure 7. The gEneSys project’s roadmap for gendered pathways in education and policy

12. Concluding Reflections

Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology

The Genesys Brussels Stakeholders Workshop demonstrated the power of participatory foresight to connect long-term visions with immediate policy and educational action. The backcasting methodology enabled participants to move beyond abstract aspirations and to identify practical steps for realising gender equality in the energy transition. By working backwards from the 2050 vision, participants were able to reveal not only what must be achieved, but also how and when transformation should occur.

A central lesson from the exercise is that equality must be treated as a system rather than a goal. Participants made clear that educational reform, policy design, financial frameworks, and cultural change form an integrated ecosystem. Progress in one domain reinforces progress in others. Backcasting made these interdependencies visible and allowed for the co-creation of a shared framework of responsibility among educators, policymakers, researchers, and citizens.

Another key reflection concerns the role of evidence and participation. The participants showed that inclusive policymaking depends on access to credible data, open communication, and collaboration across sectors. The exercise demonstrated that policy legitimacy grows when stakeholders can see their knowledge and experience reflected in future scenarios.

Finally, the workshop confirmed that cultural transformation is both the hardest and the most essential component of a just transition. Structural reforms may provide the framework, but long-term success depends on shared values and collective learning. The process of envisioning 2050 revealed that equality is not a finite goal but a continuous practice that evolves with institutions and societies.

The backcasting exercise in Brussels provided not only a roadmap for gender-just energy transitions but also a model for how participatory foresight can guide sustainable policymaking. It offered a vision of Europe in which equality, knowledge, and sustainability are inseparable foundations of the energy systems of the future.

13. References

- Bibri, SE. 2018. Backcasting in futures studies: a synthesized scholarly and planning approach to strategic smart sustainable city development. *European Journal of Futures Research* (2018) 6:13 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-018-0142-z>
- Bradfield, R., Derbyshire, J. and Wright, G. (2016). The critical role of history in scenario thinking: Augmenting causal analysis within the intuitive logics scenario development methodology. *Futures* 77 (March), 56–66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2016.02.002>.
- Dreborg, K.H., Essence of backcasting (1996). *Futures*. 28(9), 813–828, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287\(96\)00044-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287(96)00044-4).
- European Commission. 2023. How to get started with the backcasting approach. <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/rio/report/HOW%20TO%20Get%20Started%20with%20Backcasting%20Formatted%20v4.pdf> Accessed May 2025
- Genesys, 2024 Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems. URL: <https://genesys-project.eu/>
- IEA, 2021. Net Zero by 2050: A Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector. International Energy Agency. URL: https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/7ebafc81-74ed-412b-9c60-5cc32c8396e4/NetZeroBy2050-ARoadmapfortheGlobalEnergySector-SummaryforPolicyMakers_CORR.pdf Accessed December 2022
- IPCC, 2018: Summary for Policymakers. In: *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P.R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors, J.B.R. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M.I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfield (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 3-24. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157940.001>.
- IRENA. 2024. Energy Transition Outlook. URL: <https://www.irena.org/Energy-Transition/Outlook> Accessed June 2024.
- IEA 2020, *Gender diversity in energy: what we know and what we don't know – Analysis*, IEA. URL: <https://www.iea.org/commentaries/gender-diversity-in-energy-what-we-know-and-what-we-dont-know> Accessed: May 2024.
- Kok K, Rothman D, and Patel M. 2006. Multi-scale narratives from an IA perspective: Part I. *European and Mediterranean scenario development. Futures* 38 (2006) 261–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2005.07.001>
- Hivos, 2020. Beyond Fire. Backcasting a Pathway to Fully Electric Cooking in Rural Kenya by 2030. By Lambe F, Nyambane A and Bailis R. Hivos and SEI. URL: <https://hivos.org/document/beyond-fire-backcasting-a-pathway-to-fully-electric-cooking-in-rural-kenya-by-2030/> Accessed May 2025.

Co-creation of pathways and analysis of scenarios with a backcasting methodology

Leung, P (2016). Backcasting: Starting with the end in mind. Energy Futures Lab. 17 February, <https://energyfutureslab.com/backcasting-starting-with-the-end-in-mind>

Mourik, R. and Rotmann, S., 2013. Most of the time what we do is what we do most of the time. And sometimes we do something new. Analysis of Case-studies IEA DSM Task 24 Closing the Loop - Behaviour Change in DSM: from Theory to Practice. International Energy Agency Demand Side Management Technology Collaboration Programme.

Mourik, R., Robison, R., and Breukers, S. (2017). Storytelling - SHAPE ENERGY facilitation guidelines for interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder processes. Cambridge: SHAPE ENERGY.

UN, 2024. For a liveable climate: Net-zero commitments must be backed by credible action. URL: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/net-zero-coalition> Accessed May 2024.

UNWomen and UNIDO, 2023. Gender Equality and the Sustainable Energy Transition. New York and Vienna.

Wangel J. 2011. Exploring social structures and agency in backcasting studies for sustainable development. Technological Forecasting & Social Change 78 (2011) 872–882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2011.03.007> Accessed May 2025.

WRI, 2024. 5 Essential Principles of the Just Transition Work Programme for Climate Action. March 4, 2024. URL: <https://www.wri.org/technical-perspectives/5-essential-principles-just-transition-work-programme-climate-action> Accessed May 2024.

ANNEX 1

Agenda of workshop

Horizon Europe - gEneSys project co-creation workshop

Co-creating sustainable pathways for achieving gender just transformations in energy ecosystem

June 17th 2025, Registration 9.30; Programme 10.00- 16.30

Place: ENEA office, Rue de Namur, 72-74 1000 Brussels

Workshop Objectives

[gEneSys](#) envisages energy transition as a socio-technological ecosystem with several subsystems of goals, agendas, actors and stakeholders (technical, social, economic, policy, environment). The purpose of the co-creation workshop is to build mutual understanding of gender equality as a lever of achieving just and fair outcomes. The workshop will adopt a participatory approach that combines 'story-telling' (of stakeholders' activities) and a backcasting exercise to co-create the pathways. The objectives include:

1. **Sharing views for achieving gender equality benefits as outcomes of energy transition efforts**
2. **Discussing how to integrate gender mainstreaming into the implementation efforts of all EU energy policy areas, and energy transition programmes**
3. **Co-creating shared visions for gender just energy pathways that reflect the aspirations and realities of diverse stakeholders through a backcasting methodology.**

	Agenda
09:30 – 10.00	Arrivals and networking
10:00	Welcome and introductions (Imperial)
10:15	New research from gEneSys (CNR/ENEA)
10:.45	Q&A
11:00	Storytelling and reflections from stakeholders' experiences (Portia)
12:00	Co-creation pathways: Vision definition on education and policy (Imperial)
13:00	Lunch & networking
14.00	Backcasting co-creation of pathways (all)
15.00	Open discussion, recommendations and final reflections
16.00	Coffee networking

16.30	Close of session
--------------	------------------

LOGISTICS

ENEA office, Rue de Namur, 72-74 1000 Brussels

Is located close to the Prte de Namur metro station.

